

Table S2. Components of Lonza ALI base differentiation media

Components	Concentration	Supplier
BEBM	50%	Lonza, Cat#CC3171
DMEM	50%	Sigma, Cat#D5796
Hydrocortisone	0.1%	Lonza, Cat# (CC- 4031 F)
Insulin, Bovine	0.1%	Lonza, Cat# (CC – 4021 F)
Epinephrine	0.1%	Lonza, Cat# (CC – 4221 F)
Bovine Pituitary Extract	0.4%	Lonza, Cat# (CC – 4009F)
Transferrin	0.1%	Lonza, Cat# (CC – 4205F)
Ethanolamine	80 μ M	Sigma, Cat#E0135
hEGF	10 ng/ml	Bioscientific Cat#236-EG-200
All-trans retinoic acid	30ng/ml	Sigma, Cat#R2625
MgCl ₂	0.3mM	Sigma, Cat#M8266
MgSO ₄	0.4mM	Sigma, Cat#M2643
BSA	0.5mg/ml	Sigma, Cat#A8806
Penicillin/streptomycin	2%	Life Tech, Cat#15070-063
Amphotericin B solution	250 μ g/ml	Sigma, Cat#A2942